

Exploring the Efficacy of the 'AI Mind Palace' in Enhancing Assessment Preparedness and Reducing Test Anxiety

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Abstract

Contemporary research investigating the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in assessment has primarily focused on the impact of AI-generated content as a form of academic malpractice (Chan, 2024; Birks and Clare, 2023). However, in contexts where assessments are entirely exam-based, AI presents opportunities for far more constructive applications. Building on the initial snapshot study focusing on high-stakes assessments (Pickering, 2024), this research explored the longitudinal influence of a context-specific AI-powered 360-degree virtual environment, the 'AI Mind Palace,' on instruction, learning, and assessment outcomes. The study specifically examined its impact across low, medium and high-stakes experiences. In the run-up to assessments, particularly those perceived as high stakes, teachers often employ tactics they believe to be motivational, such as fear appeals. These messages emphasise the importance of high-stakes exams and the necessity of achieving certain grades for progression to further education or employment (Putwain & Symes, 2014; Putwain, Symes & McCaldin, 2017). However, while intended to motivate, fear appeals can be detrimental, causing anxiety and stress among students (Hall et al., 2004; Putwain & Roberts, 2009). The AI Mind Palace aims to counteract this by providing a supportive, familiar environment that reduces test anxiety and enhances confidence, thus promoting a more positive and effective approach to exam preparation.

The AI Mind Palace integrated a blend of AI, Virtual Reality (VR), personal computing, and mobile-friendly platforms. It was designed based on the Method of Loci (MoL), a mnemonic technique associating memory with spatial environments, and the context-dependent memory effect (Godden and Baddeley, 1975; Tulving, 1973), which suggests that reinstating the learning context enhances recall. The virtual environment consisted of both familiar (photo-generated) and unfamiliar (AI-generated) 360/VR imagery, reflecting the students' existing classroom schemas. This resource also offered self-efficacy training (Bandura, 1977), enabling students to acclimatise to the assessment environment and contributing to reducing test anxiety.

The classroom environment was enhanced with resources linked to prior learning, creating a foundation for context-dependent memory recall. Additional virtual rooms were added, allowing students to explore and learn new material within a simulated version of the examination environment. These included opportunities for low-stakes assessments, instructional videos, and AI-driven personalised revision tools. The primary objective was to reduce test anxiety by familiarising students with the exam setting while supporting retrieval practice and contextual familiarisation.

The investigation involved three groups of A-Level students ($n=28$), who used the AI Mind Palace at different stages of their two-year programme: cohort 1 (low stakes), cohort 2 (medium stakes), and cohort 3 (high stakes). Cohort 1 undertook internal end-of-topic assessments, while Cohort 2 participated in formative assessments informing their progression to year 2. Cohort 3 used the tool during their summative A-Level assessments, where final results were at stake. The AI Mind Palace was utilised individually, allowing students to navigate the virtual exam room in preparation for their assessments.

Data collection was conducted via a co-designed self-report questionnaire (Pickering and Kostrzewa, 2024), and results were analysed through correlational analysis of grades and targets, alongside thematic analysis of student experiences. Findings indicated that the AI Mind Palace significantly boosted students' confidence in navigating the exam room, reduced their anxiety, and enhanced their readiness for assessments. Cohort 3 reported the highest levels of confidence, with 90% attributing their preparedness to the tool, compared to 76% for cohorts 1 and 2. The correlation between cohort 3's confidence and their summative grades was strong ($r = 0.79$).

The research concluded that the AI Mind Palace is a valuable and innovative tool for revision, offering students the opportunity to learn in novel ways while becoming familiar with the exam context. Self-adaptive techniques driven by AI helped participants build self-efficacy over time, which was particularly beneficial for high-stakes assessments. The study also identified challenges, such as technical difficulties, accessibility issues, and the precision of AI-generated resources. Recommendations were made to address these limitations and enhance the design and implementation of the tool.

This research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on the use of AI-infused VR/360 environments in education. By demonstrating the effectiveness of integrating mnemonic strategies with AI technology, it highlights the potential for such tools to improve learning outcomes and assessment experiences. The AI Mind Palace has since been adapted for use at four other campuses, including applications tailored to reducing anxiety for students with autism spectrum disorders (ASD). These adaptations demonstrate the flexibility and potential for diversifying the tool's use to address a range of educational barriers.

References

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Themes

Digital Technology and Artificial Intelligence

Second Theme

Practitioner Research